

Effect of solvent on fabrication of Polymer Light-Emitting Diodes

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Electroluminescence from small organic molecules and polymers forms the basis for their use in light emitting diodes (OLEDs and PLEDs)[1-5]. Polymeric EL materials have drawn great attention in recent years because of their advantages of good processability, simple fabrication by solution process, and good thermal stability. However, some major hindrances, arising from the inter-chain interaction and charge imbalance between hole and electron, still need to be overcome. Using spin coating, it is expected that the preparation conditions (particularly type of the solvent used) will have an impact on the device optoelectronic properties. Polymer light emitting diodes (PLED) based on blue poly(9,9-dioctylfluorene-2,7-diyl) (PFO) was prepared using toluene and p-xylene as solvent in spin coating method. The device structure with ITO/ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PFO/Ca/Al. Photoluminescence (PL) emission peaks at 419, 440, and 468 nm were observed, device was dissolved in toluene had three electroluminescence (EL) spectra emission components at 420, 440 and 470 nm and p-xylene peaks at 425, 451, and 489 nm and one shoulder at 500nm. It was found that the solvents were influenced the emission wavelength were influenced the emission wavelength of the devices. The device using toluene and xylene solvent showed main peak emission 440 nm which is the blue emission range. The observed results suggested that the difference in solvent polarity, reactivity and vaporizing rate has strong effect the polymers in solution. The PFO which dissolves in toluene has higher luminance and current efficiency and more stable blue emission than in xylene. The poor current efficiency can be attributed to exciton quenching because recombination zone is near to the electrodes. Fig.1 shows that CIE coordinates of blue polymer light emitting diodes at various bias voltages.

Fig.1. The CIE coordinates of blue polymer light emitting diodes at various biases

In summary, we investigated that the PFO which dissolves in toluene had higher luminance and current efficiency and more stable blue emission than in p-xylene. This showed toluene was a more adaptable solvent than p-xylene for PFO. Additionally, although the maximal efficiency of toluene was higher than xylene and the poor efficiency could be attributed to exciton quenching because recombination zone was near to the cathode.

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